

METHODOLOGICAL MEANS OF PRESCHOOL EDUCATION MANAGEMENT

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ANNOTATION: The preschool institution has a managed and managing system. The controlled system consists of interconnected teams: pedagogical, medical and service. The organizational structure of management in a preschool institution is a combination of all its organs with their inherent functions.

Keywords: organizational structure, preschool education management preschool institution, kindergarten, pedagogical monitoring, quality of education.

Preschool education is a holistic process aimed at: ensuring the versatile development of a preschool child in accordance with his inclinations, inclinations, abilities, individual, mental and physical characteristics, cultural needs; the formation of moral norms in a preschool child, the acquisition of life social experience by him.

“Without spiritualization by living thought and the enthusiasm of the teacher, the method remains a dead scheme. For from the moment a little person takes his first step on earth, he begins to compare himself with the one who educates him, makes demands on him, puts his spiritual forces into him, wants to see his ideal in him. V.A. Sukhomlinsky

Organizational structure of management. It can be represented as three levels.

At the first level of management is the head of the kindergarten, which manages and controls the activities of all structures. Instructions and orders of the head are obligatory for all participants in the educational process. The general management of the institution is carried out by the pedagogical council, which includes all teachers. The Pedagogical Council decides on its activities at meetings. The Pedagogical Council is authorized to: adopt the Charter, amendments and additions to the Charter; approve the class schedule; determine the direction of educational and educational activities of the institution; approve the annual work plan of the SEI; adopt

educational and training programs in the institution; consider issues of advanced training and retraining of personnel; consider and approve the methodological directions of work with children in various groups, as well as all other issues of the content, methods and forms of the educational process;

At the second level, management is carried out by a senior educator, supply manager, head nurse, who interact with the relevant management objects. At this level, the manager directly and indirectly implements management decisions through the distribution of responsibilities between administrative workers, taking into account their training, experience, as well as the structure of the preschool institution.

The third level of management is carried out by educators, music director, physical education teacher. At this level, the object of control are children and their parents.

The organization of the pedagogical process is considered as a complex system - goals, objectives, means, forms and methods, subject, object of management, principles and functions that determine its activity.

The goals that determine the activities of the subjects of management are adequate to the goals and objectives of the pedagogical process: the development of the child's personality, the formation of his need for knowledge of the world and himself, therefore, the main condition in the activity is the recognition by all members of the team of the uniqueness of the child's personality.

The task of shaping the personality of a child - a preschooler is most successfully implemented when the managerial actions of the head of the preschool educational institution are combined with the desire of teachers to provide the child with pedagogical support in his development and formation, improve working methods, and implement their own management concept of an educational institution.

The implementation of such a concept largely depends on the totality of management principles.

"The principles of management are understood as the main provisions that guide the subject of management in its activities, carrying it out in certain socio-economic conditions."

Management principles:

- goal-setting, complexity, democratization, psychologization of models of training and education. All these principles are a guide to action in a developing and developing preschool educational institution, they are at the heart of updating its activities. In the model, we distinguish management functions that reflect the course and sequence of management actions, their completeness:
- information-analytical, control-diagnostic, planned-prognostic, regulatory-corrective, motivational-target.

The management of the pedagogical process in a preschool educational institution on a scientific basis actualizes the problem of management methods that ensure the coordination of the activities of the pedagogical team in achieving the set goals. Management methods in preschool: - organizational and administrative, psychological and pedagogical, social impact:

With the help of this group of management methods, the DOE maintains the internal routine provided for by the Charter, selects and places personnel, creates conditions for the rational organization of affairs, exactingness and personal responsibility of each employee;

psychological and pedagogical methods direct the staff of the preschool educational institution to the creative solution of the tasks; on the basis of these organizational and administrative management methods are implemented in the development and approval of annual plans, a promising development program for preschool educational institutions, decisions of the pedagogical council, while instructing performers in the form of instructions, orders, orders.

The style of work of the head, his business and personal qualities have a significant impact on the mode and procedure of work of the preschool educational institution, on the efficiency and effectiveness of its activities. Therefore, management in this institution should be based on the personal principle, since the final results of management activities are achieved not by the leader himself, but by all members of the team.

"The leadership style also creates and reproduces a special atmosphere in the team and gives rise to its own etiquette, a certain type of behavior and relationships," V. Lazarev, T. Afanasyeva note.

The rallying of teachers into a team is facilitated by holding such events in which teachers can realize their creativity, for example, pedagogical councils on the topic: "To be a member of a team

means ...", "Pedagogy of cooperation - as I understand it", discussions "My pedagogical profession", etc. The creation of a team of like-minded people is the result of effective management and at the same time the guarantee of an effectively organized pedagogical process.

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